

A NEW HIGHER-ORDER THEORY TO LAMINATED PLATES AND SHELLS

Zeng Jia-Xiong, Fan Ye-Li
 Department of Mechanics Engineering, South
 China University of Science and Technology, China

We shall present a new higher-order theory to laminated plates and shells in the paper. We suggest the assumed displacement field in a laminated plate be :

$$\begin{aligned} u &= u_0 + z\psi_x(x,y) + z^2\varphi_x(x,y) + z^3\xi_x(x,y) + z^4\eta_x(x,y) \\ v &= v_0 + z\psi_y(x,y) + z^2\varphi_y(x,y) + z^3\xi_y(x,y) + z^4\eta_y(x,y) \\ w &= w_0(x,y) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

and the assumed displacement field of a thin laminated shell be.

$$\begin{aligned} u(\xi_1, \xi_2, \zeta) &= \left(1 + \frac{\zeta}{R_1}\right) u_0 + \zeta\psi_1 + \zeta^2\varphi_1 + \xi^3\vartheta_1 + \xi^4\eta_1 \\ v(\xi_1, \xi_2, \zeta) &= \left(1 + \frac{\zeta}{R_2}\right) v_0 + \zeta\psi_2 + \zeta^2\varphi_2 + \xi^3\vartheta_2 + \xi^4\eta_2 \\ w(\xi_1, \xi_2, \zeta) &= w_0(\xi, \xi_2) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Therefore, in a shell of orthotropic laminas, refer to the condition that the shears on the surfaces vanish, We can infer the displacement field as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} u &= \left(1 + \frac{\zeta}{R_1}\right) u_0 + \zeta\psi_1 + \zeta\varphi_1 - \frac{4}{3h^2}\zeta^3\left(\varphi_1 + \frac{1}{\alpha_1}\frac{\partial\omega}{\partial\xi}\right) - \frac{2}{h^2}\zeta^4\varphi_1 \\ v &= \left(1 + \frac{\zeta}{R_2}\right) v_0 + \zeta\psi_2 + \zeta\varphi_2 - \frac{4}{3h^2}\zeta^3\left(\varphi_2 + \frac{1}{\alpha_2}\frac{\partial\omega}{\partial\xi_2}\right) - \frac{2}{h^2}\zeta^4\varphi_2 \\ w &= w_0(\xi_1, \xi_2) \end{aligned}$$

We can deduce the equilibrium equations of a shell by the principle of virtual displacement. If we substitute the constitutive relations into the preceding equations, we can acquire the equilibrium equations expressed by displacement functions. In order to examine the accuracy of the theory this paper offers, symmetric and antisymmetric cross-ply laminated plates, cylindrical bending and bending to spherical shells are also studied, respectively. From the numerical results we come to the conclusions as follows:

1. The examples above about plates and shells display that the higher-order theory offered in this paper possesses high accuracy. It can be seen from the results that with this both deflection and in-plane stress are more exact than with first-order shear theory.

2. The authors have also calculated cylindrical bending of plates. The results is much closed to that form pagano's theory and indicates this theory is in good agreement with the exact theory.

3. This thory wants less unknowns than LCW theory and is conrenient in application. The computation can be carrjed out by small computers.